

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF RESIN CURE USING A GENERAL PURPOSE FE PACKAGE

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SUMMARY: This paper proposes a procedure for using a general purpose finite element package with a transient thermal analysis facility to perform cure modelling. In the procedure, a general purpose finite element package was employed to carry out transient thermal analysis and a user program was developed to simulate the cure kinetics using nodal control volumes based on the finite element mesh. Theoretical background and numerical implementation of the procedure are described in the paper.

Application of the procedure was demonstrated by modelling the curing of a 140 layer T300/3501-6 uni-directional prepreg laminate in an autoclave as a one-dimensional as well as a three-dimensional problem. The stability of the procedure with the mesh density and length of the time step used was investigated. The temperature profiles predicted by the present approach were in excellent agreement with the available experimental data.

KEYWORDS: resin cure, finite element thermal analysis, nodal control volume

INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing of fibre reinforced composite parts are complex, require special environment and can be costly to control. This is because the composites consist of two different material systems, namely fibre and matrix systems. Most commonly used fibres are glass, aramid, boron, carbon and graphite while matrices are generally thermosetting resins. The successful production of a composite part depends mainly upon the use of a proper cure cycle that leads to complete and uniform curing. As a high exothermic reaction is a characteristics of curing of thermoset resins, the temperature profiles in the curing part depend upon not only the amount of heating power supplied to the tool but also the amount of heat generated by the resin cure reaction. The generated heat is a function of the total mass fraction of resin in the mould and the resin system used. The exothermic reaction associated with low thermal conductivity can lead to excessively high temperatures at some locations in the part and, as a consequence, result in a non-uniform state of cure. Therefore, it is desirable to study the effects of this temperature rise when setting up a cure cycle for the component.

It has been proven that the process of resin cure and the related thermal response of the component can be modelled relatively accurately by a numerical method, such as the finite element method [1-4]. However, most of the results reported were obtained using specially developed programs in which two major tasks of the cure modelling: solution of the discretised energy equations and simulation of the cure kinetics, are coupled. Development of

such a program is usually lengthy and costly, especially when a three-dimensional geometry and complicated boundary/interface conditions are to be accommodated.

This paper proposes a procedure by which a general purpose finite element package can be employed to perform cure modelling. The theoretical background and numerical implementation of the procedure are described. The application of the procedure to the cure modelling of a thick graphite/epoxy prepreg laminate with and without considering the three-dimensional heat transfer effect, is presented. The results obtained were in excellent agreement with the experimental data.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Governing Equations

For simplicity, let us consider a prepreg moulding process. In this case, the resin is more or less evenly distributed in a prepreg lay-up and the convective heat transfer effect caused by the resin flow can be safely ignored. It is also assumed that the resin and fibres are at the same temperature at any point in the curing composite and form a macroscopically homogeneous material system for heat transfer purpose. Under these assumptions, the energy equation governing heat transfer in the curing product is simplified as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(K_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(K_y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = \rho_c \cdot c_p \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_c , c_p , and K_i ($i = x, y, z$) are lumped density, specific heat and directional thermal conductivities of the lay-up material respectively.

The internal heat generation source term $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t}$ represents the exothermic effect of the resin reaction. By ignoring the effect of resin flow on the species, it is related to the rate of cure directly by the following equation:

$$\rho_c \frac{dQ}{dt} = \rho_r V_r Q_{total} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where, α is the degree of cure which is defined as the ratio of the heat released to the total heat of reaction, Q_{total} is total heat of reaction and, $\rho_r V_r$ is mass content of the resin.

Cure Reaction Kinetics

The heat release rate for a particular resin system can be determined by a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) experiment. The experimental data obtained from DSC is usually fitted into some semi-empirical model representing the rate of cure as a function of temperature and the degree of cure. One of the most frequently used and simplest model is the following Arrhenius relation [5-8]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = f(T, \alpha) = B(1 - \alpha)^C \exp(-\Delta E / RT) \quad (3)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is absolute temperature, B , ΔE and C are material constants to be determined by the experiment.

In some cases, it is more accurate to fit the data by two Arrhenius equations [8]. Namely, one have:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \begin{cases} B_1 \cdot (1-\alpha)^{C_1} \exp(-\Delta E_1 / RT) & \alpha \leq A \\ B_2 (1-\alpha)^{C_2} \exp(-\Delta E_2 / RT) & \alpha > A \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Let $B_r = B \exp(-\Delta E / RT)$, Eqn 3 can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{1}{(1-\alpha)^c} d\alpha = B_r dt \quad (5)$$

Integrating Eqn 5 produces:

$$\alpha = 1 - [1 + (C-1)S]^{\frac{1}{1-C}} \quad (c \neq 1) \quad (6)$$

where S is an integral:

$$S = \int_{t_0}^t B_r d\theta = B \int_{t_0}^t \exp(-\Delta E / RT) d\theta \quad (7)$$

Adapting an explicit scheme, the integral can be evaluated approximately as:

$$S_t = S_{t_0} + B \exp(-\Delta E / RT_{t_0}) \Delta t \quad t \in [t_0, t_0 + \Delta t] \quad (8)$$

Once S is evaluated for a time step, α , $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ and $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t}$ can be calculated using Eqns 6, 4 and 2 respectively.

NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION

Solution Procedure

From the above presentation, it is obvious that cure modelling can indeed be considered as a transient heat transfer analysis by taking into account the effect of the resin cure reaction. Numerically, It can be divided into two sub-tasks: formulation and solution of the heat transfer equations, and simulation of the cure kinetics. Although most of the general purpose finite element packages can be used to perform the first sub-task, they usually do not provide facility to evaluate the cure kinetics.

A procedure is proposed in which a general purpose finite element package is employed to perform transient thermal analysis and a user program is developed to simulate the cure reaction using nodal control volumes based on the finite element mesh. Once the temperature field is obtained by the finite element analysis, the user program is activated to simulate the cure kinetics and heat generation at each of the nodal control volumes. These are then lumped and applied as heat sources at those nodal points for the finite element transient thermal analysis of next time step. This can easily be achieved through modification of the input data

file to the finite element package. If necessary, a few iterations can be performed to achieve higher accuracy. The procedure is repeated until the curing process completes. The modelling process is automated by executing the user program and the finite element package alternatively in batch mode. Fig. 1 illustrates the flow chart of the procedure.

Fig. 1: Flow chart of the cure modelling procedure.

Numerical Evaluation of Nodal Heat Sources

The major computation involved in the user program is the evaluation of the equivalent nodal heat sources caused by the cure reaction. In this paper, the evaluation is conducted based on the finite element nodal control volumes.

A control volume is an/a area/volume over which the parameters such as temperature, pressure, etc., are assumed to be constant. The concept of nodal control volumes has been successfully used by investigators for the flow simulation [2,3,5]. In this technique, initially sub-control volumes are created by connecting a centroid of the finite element to the center-points of its surfaces. The boundary of each sub-control volume contains only one finite element node and that volume is assumed to be linked to that particular node. This way, all the sub-control volumes surrounding the node formulate a nodal control volume, see Fig. 2. Heat generated within the volume is then lumped as a point heat source applied at the node.

Once the finite element mesh is defined, all the geometrical data are available and can be used to calculate the area/volume of each of the control volumes.

Fig. 2: Nodal control volume based on finite element mesh.

The resin content of control volume j can be determined as:

$$V_r^j = V^j V_r \quad (9)$$

where, V_r^j : resin content of control volume j , V^j : area/volume of control volume j , V_r : resin volume fraction.

Total heat generated in control volume j is:

$$Q^j = (Q_{Total}) V_r^j \cdot \frac{d\alpha^j}{dt} \quad (10)$$

This is applied as a lumped heat source at nodal point j .

CURE MODELLING OF A THICK LAMINATE

Modelling Conditions

The procedure was applied to simulate the curing process of a thick square laminate in autoclave as a one-dimensional as well as a three-dimensional problem. The same problem was analysed using CURE, a specially developed finite difference cure modelling program [8]. The laminate was made up of 140 plies of T300/3501-6 uni-directional prepreg. The bagging materials were assumed to be a combination of one layer of release film, two of breather and one of nylon. Geometric details of the tooling configuration are shown in Fig. 3. Physical properties of the tooling, prepreg and bagging materials are given in Table 1. Reaction kinetics of Hercules 3501-6 resin system can be expressed by Eqn 4 [8]. Table 2 lists the parameters in the equation.

Fig. 3: Cross section of tooling configuration.

Table 1: Physical properties used in the model

Material	Aluminium	T300/ 3501-6	Bagging
Density [kg/m ³]	2692.12	1555.00	355.65
Specific Heat [J/kg. K]	916.91	909.00	1256.0
Conductivity [W/m. K]	216.30	0.556	0.069

Table 2: Parameters in cure kinetics model for Hercules 3501-6 resin system

Q_{total} (J/kg)	A	B_1	B_2	ΔE_1 (J/mol)	ΔE_2 (J/mol)	C_1	C_2
3.8×10^5	0.18	3.49×10^8	2.53×10^5	94828	73445	10	1.2

The one-dimensional model of the laminate, as shown in Fig. 4a, was created using different number of 4-noded quadrilateral field elements. The three-dimensional model of a quarter (because of 2-axis symmetry) of the laminate fabrication assembly is illustrated in Fig. 4b which consisted of 210 (49 for the tool, 80 for the laminate and 81 for the bagging), 8-noded solid field elements.

Fig. 4: Finite element models.

As reported by Vodicka [8], a heat transfer coefficient of $85\text{W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ was used between the autoclave air and the tool/bagging materials in the present analysis. The autoclave temperature cycle adapted is given in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Autoclave temperature cycle.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the stability of the procedure, the problem was first analysed using different number of elements and different size of time increments in one-dimensional modelling. No iterations were applied in the analysis. Fig. 6 illustrates temperature response in the central layer of the laminate. Very negligible variations were observed. This suggests that the results are not sensitive to both the mesh density and the size of time increment. In the following analyses, a 30 seconds time step was used with no iteration performed.

a. different finite element mesh density.

b. different time increments.

Fig. 6: Temperature response at central lamina

Using the same computational conditions, the problem was modelled using both the present procedure and CURE. The temperature results obtained for the central layer were compared with the experimental data in Fig. 7. Also shown in the figure is the simulated temperature response without considering the exothermic effect.

The results indicated that both procedures predicted temperature responses generally in good agreement with the experimental result. However, the result obtained by CURE tended to shift away from the true response after the temperature overshoot caused by the exothermic effect. The maximum temperature predicted by the present model and CURE was 207.1°C and 210.6°C respectively while the experimental value was 205.6°C . The exothermic effect of resin cure is obvious, causing a temperature overshoot of more than 25°C in the central layer. This highlights the need for a cure modelling to be conducted for the thick laminate.

Fig. 7: Temperature response at central lamina obtained by different methods.

At the initial stage of the cure cycle, autoclave temperature was hold at 55°C for 80 minutes to allow the temperature in the tooling set-up to homogenise. Very negligible cure ($\alpha=0.0013$) was observed during this stage. Therefore, this segment of the cure cycle was ignored in three-dimensional analysis to save the computational efforts. Significant solidification was observed from 126.5 minute. The degree of cure at central lamina reached a value of 0.6 (approximate gel point) at 138.0 minute and 0.95 at 156.5 minute, see Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Degree of cure at central lamina Vs. time (1D simulation).

Fig. 9 compares the temperature responses at the centre of the laminate predicted by one-dimensional and three-dimensional simulations respectively. The two predictions were generally in good agreement, giving the highest temperatures of 207.1°C and 207.0°C respectively. The temperature predicted by one-dimensional analysis had a slower rate of decrease after the temperature overshoot as compared to the three-dimensional result. This is because that in one-dimensional analysis heat could only be dissipated into the air from the top and bottom surfaces, while in three-dimensional analysis additional dissipation was allowed from the edges.

Fig. 9: Temperature response by 1D and 3D Cure Modelling using present procedure

To further investigate the edge effect which can only be considered by three-dimensional analysis, temperature contours of the central lamina at two different timings are illustrated in Fig. 10. At the early stage of curing, there was little reaction and heat was transferred from the autoclave air into the laminate through the tooling/air interface. Therefore, temperatures at central locations were lower than those of the positions close to the interface. At the later stage, significant exothermic effect of curing caused higher temperature in the laminate than that of the autoclave air and heat was dissipated from the laminate to the air. Temperature was then decreasing from the centre of the laminate to the interface. Maximum temperature difference observed for the central lamina was 8°C.

Fig. 10: Temperature contours in the central lamina.

Fig. 11 shows temperature distribution in thickness direction at 139 minutes. Since the bagging materials have very low thermal conductivity, heat was very difficult to dissipate from the top surface. This resulted in a temperature difference of about 20°C in thickness direction. Such a significant difference in temperature would affect the uniformity of the cure. Fig. 12 gives the distribution of α at the corresponding sections. A 10% difference in the degree of cure was observed.

Fig. 11: Temperatures after 139 minutes of curing.

Fig. 12: Degree of cure after 139 minutes of curing.

CONCLUSIONS

A procedure was proposed to employ a general purpose finite element package in cure modelling for composite manufacturing. Thus, the costly development of a numerical thermal analysis program can be avoided. The procedure was validated by the simulation of the curing process for a 140 layer T300/3501-6 laminate. It can be concluded that

1. The procedure is numerically stable and produces more accurate results than the specially developed finite difference cure modelling program CURE.
2. The procedure can make use of all the features pertaining to the finite element package used. Therefore, cure modelling for composite parts with complicated geometry and material properties can be conducted by the procedure. In particular, it can perform three-dimensional cure modelling.
3. The results of cure modelling for the thick laminate indicate that the one-dimensional simulation can only predict the temperature and the degree of cure along the central axis of the laminate. A three-dimensional simulation should be performed if more accurate and comprehensive results are required.

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